

Event Management Report

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(T8.7) Event Management

The Project Ô Description of Action states that there should be ‘1 Event for each demo site’ aimed at engaging the local community stakeholders and other events aimed at ‘close’ and ‘extended’ networks. The full Project Ô programme of events organised by the Institute for Methods Innovation (IMI) engaged a total of 577 participants (about double the official target in the project DoA of 290 event participants).

Table 1. *Project Ô full event programme*

Event	Date
<i>Public engagement: Spain</i>	15-16 June 2022
<i>International professional event: Impact planning using logic models and theory of change</i>	31 August 2022
<i>Public engagement: Italy</i>	22 September 2022
<i>Public engagement: Croatia</i>	19 October 2022
<i>International professional event: How to make a difference in science policy with your research</i>	21 November 2022
<i>Public engagement: Israel</i>	22 November 2022

This report documents a series of public engagement events that were planned and delivered with a focus on engaging with local publics and non-expert communities. These events informed the direction and implementation of Project Ô innovations, enabling the project to listen to concerns and hopes about the future of circular water economy solutions. This report discusses co-creation events that took place between June and November 2022 in Spain, Italy, Croatia, and Israel as part of Project Ô's communication efforts (four local co-creation events)¹. Finally, the report presents details of the international events organised by the project, which were aimed at a broad international professional audience. This report also documents each public engagement event, including the delivery of information, the co-creation activity, context, information gathering, and results. A description of each event is provided as an independent case study. The concluding section discusses the implications of the key findings.

¹ The coordinator determined that four co-creation events would take place for the project.

Local Co-creation Public Engagement Events: Event Case Studies and Key Findings

In this section, each public engagement event is documented, including content delivery, co-creation activity, context, information gathering, and results. Public participation in these events highlighted pre-knowledge, attitudes, expectations, and concerns relevant to the project. Diverse groups of stakeholders provided insights on public views of water management, sustainability, and innovation, generally, and Project Ô technologies and approaches to promoting a circular water economy, specifically. The public engagement activities were designed to inform the work during the project, as well as foreground issues relevant to other water reuse initiatives within and outside the European Union.

The Institute for Methods Innovation (IMI) team engaged extensively with demosite partners and the project coordinator to try to involve other partners in the public engagement co-creation event organisation process. Ultimately, IMI took primary responsibility for the design, delivery, data collection, management and analysis of these co-creation events. In Spain, collaboration with a sister water sustainability project called CIRCULAR BIOCARBON was successfully implemented with a face-to-face 2-day public engagement event in Almendralejo.

For this event, practical adjustments were made to ensure that both projects gained what was needed. For the other three demosite locations, the public engagement events were fully organised by IMI, with demosite partners attending and encouraged to invite known contacts to attend with them. IMI took responsibility for all aspects of event organisation, administration and follow-up. Practical tasks involved in the event management process implemented by IMI included:

- Liaising with demosite partners and other stakeholders
- Preparing targeted outreach messaging for local members of the public to gain their participation
- Recruiting and liaising with workshop participants
- Determination of workshop approach and outline of the agenda Workshop scheduling and practical organisation

- Registration for workshops
- Ensuring GDPR and informed consent is obtained prior to any workshop data collection commencing
- Preparation of workshop materials (including invitations, worksheets, slide decks)
- Subtitling relevant project videos for workshop purposes
- Development, translation and adaptation of templates for local language and context
- Updating participants, answering queries and ongoing participant communications
- Managing the practicalities of the meeting, ensuring high-quality data collection and participant experience through skilled workshop facilitation
- Recording the session to allow for data collection, and quality assurance
- Transcription, translation and management of recorded data
- Documentation of participants' perspectives through note-taking and data analysis
- Ensure that participant preferences for anonymisation/confidentiality are fully implemented and all ethical guidelines are followed
- GDPR-compliant data management, storage, analysis and reporting
- Participant feedback survey preparation, delivery and analysis

The co-creation events have been structured to deliver the project's objectives relating to public involvement and stakeholder engagement. Engaging the local community close to each demosite was a key requirement in the project to improve social acceptance and enhance the project's impact. IMI spent a great deal of time working to engage other project partners (particularly demosites), with the aim of including them in this process. However, the skills to deliver this kind of work were not widely available, meaning that IMI had to take on considerably more responsibilities than was originally foreseen. The process began with development of an event management strategy and then a detailed plan. A series of templates and guidelines were prepared to address all aspects of the co-creation events from first contacting potential participants until post-event follow-up communications.

The events were structured in a way that would ensure community participants with no previous information about the project or related topics could fully engage. This required an initial introduction to orient participants,

including a tour of the demosite and its planned technology implementation, and establish a shared basis for subsequent discussions. This was followed by data collection exploring community members' views about the demosite implementation in their area and general themes relevant to the project. The final part of the co-creation event was aimed at drawing out creative contributions from community members to express their understanding of circular water economy innovations in their own words. Expert event facilitators from IMI were critical to the process, because we needed to balance the need to inform participants about relevant developments in their community on the one hand, with the need to gather data about their own perspectives on the other hand. Results from the co-creation events are presented in this report and have been communicated to project partners.

Co-creation public engagement event report: Spain

Synergies were identified between Project Ô and CIRCULAR BIOCARBON2, another EU-funded project (GA No. 101023280). On this basis, a series of collaborative meetings and documentation were organised by IMI with the CIRCULAR BIOCARBON coordination team and Project Ô demosite partner SOCAMEX. The public engagement co-creation event was collaboratively organised in the planning phase as a joint communication effort between the two projects.

The combined public engagement co-creation event, titled “From waste to resources in the primary sector,” was held over two days on the 15th and 16th of June 2022. The workshop involved stakeholders in activities and discussions about water sustainability and solid waste reuse specific to the primary sector, including project key concepts and innovations. To increase inclusiveness, the event was delivered in a hybrid modality, allowing for both online and in-person participation.

Figure 1. Invitation for the co-creation workshop in Almendralejo, Spain

Image credit: Daniela Martin | Institute for Methods Innovation

Local Water Sustainability Context

Almendralejo, a city in the province of Badajoz, Extremadura, Spain, is home to numerous primary sector industries, especially agriculture. Several factors indicate the merits of adopting circular water economy solutions in this region, such as large quantities of heavy waste, toxic substances that impede the breakdown of organic matter, and increasingly severe drought conditions in the region. The two EU projects involved in the public engagement activity are focused on challenges associated with wastewater material reuse. Project Ô’s

² <https://circularbiocarbon.eu/>

MOBILE3TECH technology increases the sustainable reuse of wastewater by integrating an adaptive, customised system comprised of three technologies that assess toxicity, pre-treat as needed, and apply a final treatment to ensure that water is thoroughly and efficiently cleaned in order to once again help meet human needs. This technology reduces the demands on finite water.

Technologies from the CIRCULAR BIOCARBON project will support the improvement of agricultural yields in Almendralejo by turning organic solid waste into added-value products, such as fertilisers. These products will be tailored to the specific needs of the beneficiaries with the aim to outperform the products currently used. The workshop collaboration between Project Ô and CIRCULAR BIOCARBON highlighted innovations of relevance and potential benefit to the primary sector in Almendralejo.

Water Sustainability Public Engagement Event

The first day of the co-creation event was 15 June 2022. Policymakers and representatives from the primary sector were gathered to visit the Almendralejo Wastewater Treatment Plant (WWTP) where Project Ô's MOBILE3TECH treatment module is installed. Fourteen stakeholders participated in the event. Local partners included SOCAMEX and Urbaser.

Figure 2. Co-creation workshop in Almendralejo, Spain

Image credit: Urbaser S.A.

Figure 3. Co-creation workshop in Almendralejo, Spain

Image credit: Urbaser S.A.

Figure 4. Co-creation workshop in Almendralejo, Spain

Image credit: Urbaser S.A.

On the second day of the event, 16 June 2022, a live online workshop was held with the local Almendralejo community. This session was facilitated by the Institute for Methods Innovation team and was delivered in Spanish to maximise inclusivity, including translations for all presentation materials, such as slide decks and handouts, and the subsequent transcription of the session. The workshop provided an overview of both projects and key concepts, followed by a recorded group discussion intended to unearth attitudes and perspectives on water sustainability and solid waste reuse concerns and hopes.

Figure 5. Screenshots from the co-creation workshop in Almendralejo, Spain

Co-Creation Group Discussion Findings

The co-creation group discussion portion of the workshop asked stakeholders to consider topics in-depth, for example water availability in different areas, the economic impacts of water scarcity and decreased water quality, regulations on crops grown in different geographical areas of Almendralejo, communication strategies to engage with the public and raise awareness, and benefits of engaging with Project Ô and CIRCULAR BIOCARBON technologies. Participants were asked about their concern, hopes and expectations relating to water sustainability in their area. The key concerns are outlined below.

Water Sustainability Concerns

Participants were most concerned about **water availability** in their local area. Water availability is area-specific and does not necessarily threaten every citizen equally:

“Citizens may see their quality of life endangered. Unfortunately, this concern does not apply to everyone, as the availability of water depends on the area in which they live.” (Consumer stakeholder, Female)

Concerns about water availability exist and are a daily reality.

Participant,
Spain co-creation
workshop

The shortage of water resources were identified as more urgent in particular regions, such as Alange, Spain, where the reservoir capacity has reduced substantially:

“In Mérida, the Alange reservoir has less than 20% of its water capacity remaining. The local population is living in a critical situation.” (Industry stakeholder, Male)

Participants clarified that the level of concern about **water scarcity** depends on the geographic, social, and environmental conditions:

“The level of concern about water availability depends on geographical location and socio-environmental conditions.” (Consumer stakeholder, Female)

Participants noted concerns about the broader economic implications of water scarcity and micro-level impact on how businesses operate:

“If there is not enough water, companies could not continue their productive process and this could have broader economic impacts.” (Consumer stakeholder, Female)

In addition, participants mentioned the economic impacts of water scarcity on leisure activities:

“Leisure activities may also be affected (e.g. water parks, public swimming pools, public fountains), generating an economic impact.” (Consumer stakeholder, Female)

Furthermore, there are concerns over **water quality** as a direct consequence of water scarcity. If there is water scarcity, this would impact water quality, according to this participant:

“The lower the quantity of water, the lower the water quality because there is less volume in which pollutants can be diluted.” (Consumer stakeholder, Male)

Because of an increase in pollutants, this would mean the price of treating water will be higher:

“Higher concentrations of pollutants in water are leading to an increase in the use of chemical treatment agents, which makes water more expensive and has economic implications for both consumers and businesses.” (Industry stakeholder, Male)

As with concerns about water availability, water quality concerns are also area specific:

“There are several municipalities in which tap water cannot be consumed.” (Consumer stakeholder, Male)

Participant,
Spain co-creation workshop

In addition to concerns over water quality, participants in Spain shared concerns about the controls necessary to safeguard water quality and health:

“Poor water management/treatment can have a significant impact on public health.” (Industry stakeholder, Female)

Participants also discussed the importance of an appropriate strategy to **effectively communicate the problem of water scarcity** to shore up public confidence.

“If communication is poorly managed, it can lead to general panic.”

(Consumer stakeholder, Female)

This concern about water management in Spain being distorted for political reasons was noted repeatedly during the workshop.

“What is being communicated about the state of water is politicised and has many nuances. For example, the information given about the Guadiana river on the EU website is incorrect.”

(Industry stakeholder, Male)

One of the main concerns in this area is to have **adequate regulations of water overuse**, both for citizens and for the primary sector. There is a need to regulate wells that are built and used by citizens:

“Groundwater is being drained by wells built by citizens. Many of them are illegal or unregulated.” (Industry stakeholder, Male)

There is also a general need for consideration and solidarity between those who use water:

“People take water only for themselves and do not consider the needs of others.” (Consumer stakeholder, Male)

Different types of crops require different amounts of water, which could increase water scarcity:

“We need to start regulating the type of crops grown in the area. For example, the irrigation of avocados requires more water, which has an impact on the environment and makes production more expensive.” (Industry stakeholder, Male)

The problem lies in the choice of crops. There are crops that end up being more of a luxury than a necessity because they require a lot of water.

Participant,
Spain co-creation workshop

There are also concerns over political influences in water management:

“Water managers face political pressures that affect their final decisions.” (Industry stakeholder, Male)

Water Sustainability Hopes and Expectations

One of the main expectations mentioned was to raise **public awareness** of the problem. Storytelling is one way to raise awareness about water scarcity issues:

“It is necessary to use storytelling techniques to provoke an emotional resonance and generate collective awareness.”
(Consumer stakeholder, Female)

Another way to increase public awareness by educating people about water reuse:

“There is a need for education on responsible water use. Currently there is more indiscriminate consumption, which shows a reversal in water use behaviour.” (Industry stakeholder, Female)

Another expectation was that there would be greater awareness of **water use in irrigation** in relation to the hydrological characteristics of different geographical areas. According to this participant, indigenous crops should be prioritised over other species:

“We need to establish regulations on the type of crops grown in different geographical areas. We need to favour endemic species in order to avoid invasive species.” (Policy stakeholder, Male)

This participant agrees that crops with lower water requirements should be favoured:

“We need to find the best value for water. For example, irrigation of avocado trees in unsuitable areas can consume large volumes of water with low-volume production. On the other hand, there are crops that consume a lot of water but generate a large volume of product, such as rice.” (Industry stakeholder, Female)

We need to find the **best value for water**, where there is the right balance between cost, quality and sustainability to meet human needs.

Participant,
Spain co-creation workshop

Participants also expressed the hope that in the near future they will be able to **avoid water loss** altogether:

“We need to prevent water loss at the domestic level and also at the industrial level.” (Industry stakeholder, Male)

Maintenance of water treatment plants should be undertaken regularly to avoid unnecessary losses:

“Water infrastructures, such as WWTPs, must be constantly maintained to ensure that not a drop of water is lost.” (Industry stakeholder, Male)

Circular economy solutions can help increase water reuse opportunities, according to this participant.

“We hope that this type of technology (referring to Project Ô water treatment module) will allow us to reuse 100% of the water.” (Industry stakeholder, Female)

Co-creation Activity Result

The final stage of the event was a co-creation activity in which participants were asked to create and share news stories about either the future of water sustainability in their local areas or innovations at the demonstration sites. The participants opted to write a news article about their hopes for a mobile tanker truck, containing the MOBILE3TECH water treatment module, that could collect wastewater from domestic septic tanks and transform it into water suitable for human needs. This particular story sheds light on their hopes to make these water treatment technologies accessible to communities.

Figure 6. News article created by participants during the co-creation workshop in Spain

THE TRUCK THAT TRANSFORMS WATER

SOCAMEX, in collaboration with the CNRS, the Polytechnic University of Valencia and the Technion in Israel, has developed a prototype tanker truck incorporating a pioneering water regeneration system called MOBILE3TECH.

This truck can collect wastewater from domestic septic tanks and transform it into water suitable for human consumption, as well as for irrigation of avocado and grapefruit fields.

The tanker can also travel to remote areas and small villages to treat water directly on site to meet the specific needs of each location.

The director of the Almendralejo WWTP, Pedro Sánchez, expects this modular solution to be replicated in 15 other municipalities in the coming year.

Citizens will be able to identify the tanker truck by means of a melody transmitted by a megaphone so that they can prepare their wastewater in advance.

Co-creation public engagement event report: Italy

A live, online co-creation event was held on 22 September 2022 with people from the Puglia region who were interested in the topic of circular water management. As in other locations, the event programme included an overview of Project Ô, a facilitated group discussion, and a co-creation activity. The first part of the programme was informational while the second part was oriented towards data collection and co-creation. All participant communications for the event, and the event itself, used the Italian language to ensure wide participation from the local community.

Figure 7. Invitation and agenda screenshots for the co-creation workshop in Puglia, Italy

Project Ô
Innovative circular water systems

Sei invitato/a a partecipare al workshop online

Introduzione al Project Ô:

Sviluppare strumenti pratici per la sostenibilità dell'acqua

PARTECIPATE TRAMITE ZOOM

DATA
22 Settembre 2022

ORA
9:00 - 12:00 (CET)

ID Riunione: 881 2272 9356
Password: 340491
Link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/88122729356?pwd=U3hHd25UMTEyRmE1REFxZmR6dWVhZz09>

Per qualsiasi informazione aggiuntiva, non esitate a contattarci per mail a questo indirizzo daniela@methodsinnovation.org

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Horizon 2022 dell'Unione Europea
N° di progetto 77585

Workshop online

Introduzione al Project Ô: Sviluppare strumenti pratici per la sostenibilità dell'acqua

PROGRAMMA:

09:00	Apertura e introduzioni
09:15	Presentazione del Project Ô
09:25	Discussione sulla sostenibilità dell'acqua
10:00	Pausa
10:15	Attività di co-creazione: Creazione di una notizia
11:00	Pausa
11:15	Presentazione delle notizie
11:30	Feedback e dibattito finale
11:45	Chiusura

Image credit: Daniela Martin | Institute for Methods Innovation

Local Water Sustainability Context

Groundwater resources supply over 200 wells in southern Italy and have helped to sustain the Puglia region for years. Over time, though, these wells have become contaminated with seawater and harmful bacteria. In addition, the wells are located too far away to rely on existing water treatment plants.

Project Ô's ADV.ERT filtration technology module is installed at the Cozza Guardati well in Lecce, in southern Italy's Puglia Region. This technology removes harmful bacteria and excess salt from the water. It also reduces potential harmful levels of pesticides and pharmaceuticals that could be present in the water, making it clean and safe for essential human needs such as drinking and farming. Project Ô's ADV.ERT technology can be operated as a remote unit directly at the water source, making it especially beneficial in remote locations like the wells in the Puglia region.

Water Sustainability Public Engagement Event

The live online co-creation workshop was facilitated by the Institute for Methods Innovation team and was delivered in Italian to maximise inclusivity, including local adaptations and translations for all presentation materials, such as slide decks and handouts, and the subsequent transcription of the session.

Figure 8. Screenshot from the co-creation workshop in Puglia, Italy

Co-Creation Group Discussion Findings

The group discussion portion of the workshop asked stakeholders to consider topics in-depth, including impacts of climate change on local water availability, lack of legislation on water reuse in Italy, and the need for water reuse. When asked about their perspectives on water sustainability concerns and future expectations, participants expressed the following:

Climate change is making the management, and the treatment of this resource [water] even more complex.

Participant,
Italy co-creation workshop

Water Sustainability Concerns

Climate change and its impact on water availability was one of the major concerns raised by participants during the workshop. This has an impact on water availability in the region:

“Climate change has aggravated the water scarcity situation in the Puglia region.”
(Policy stakeholder, Female)

We are a region with very little water, so I think the biggest concerns are due to this [factor].

Participant,
Italy co-creation workshop

In addition, this has affected weather patterns in the area:

“Rainfall is no longer as predictable as it used to be due to climate change. This has made water harvesting and accumulation almost impossible.” (Policy stakeholder, Male)

Another concern was the **lack of legislation on water reuse** in Italy. This participant expressed a need for increased monitoring:

“We need to monitor water bodies and water resources.” (Policy stakeholder, Male)

The more [water] we have now, the more we will have in the future.

Participant,
Italy co-creation workshop

In addition, water reuse opportunities should also be regulated:

“There is no legislation from the perspective of water reuse opportunities. For example, the issue of water conservation has not been considered in new legislatures to promote energy conservation.” (Policy stakeholder, Female)

Water Sustainability Hopes and Expectations

One of the main hopes was that there would be a growing change in attitudes and behaviour towards **water reuse**. Conserving water is everyone’s responsibility, according to this participant:

“We need everyone to start saving and reusing water as much as possible.” (Policy stakeholder, Male)

By reusing water, costs can be saved, according to this participant:

“There is a need to increase the volume of water reused in agriculture to save money.” (Policy stakeholder, Male)

In the future it would be appropriate to create a resilience plan on the only common good that truly unites all of us. It seems like we have forgotten about it: **the water.**

Participant,
Italy co-creation workshop

More water should be treated to the extent that it can be reused as drinking water:

“We could be closer to adopting a circular system if we manage to increase the volume of treated water used as drinking water.” (Policy stakeholder, Female)

Education about water reuse is also critical:

“We hope to bring about a change in the mindset of citizens. We have to make them aware that (i) reused water is of the same (if not higher) quality than what people are used to, and that (ii) the circular economy benefits the community.” (Policy stakeholder, Male)

By changing people’s mindsets, water can be increasingly reused:

“This change in citizens' mindset can be crucial. And it can start with basic actions such as reusing water from the sink, storing rainwater for watering the garden, etc.”
(Policy stakeholder, Male)

Another hope was that water bodies would be **protected through legislation:**

“We need to pay more attention to the legislative and political side if we really want to protect water bodies.” (Policy stakeholder, Female)

Plan a project with funding in the field of water management which can be handed down over time to future generations, because they will have to deal with this criticality.

Participant,
Italy co-creation workshop

This participant suggested that water reuse be made mandatory:

“One option is to make water reuse mandatory.” (Policy stakeholder, Female)

Co-creation Activity Result

The final stage of the event was a co-creation activity in which participants were asked to create and share news stories about either the future of water sustainability in their local areas or Project Ô innovations at the demonstration site. Participants wrote a fictional story about the need for more water treatment plants in the region to meet the demand of citizens and farmers. Participants opted to write about a Utopian scenario, reflecting their hopes for water sustainability in the Puglia region, as part of the co-creation workshop in Italy. This particular story sheds light on their hopes to adopt a circular system by increasing the volume of water treated to meet human needs.

Figure 9. News article created by participants during the co-creation workshop in Italy

BY POPULAR DEMAND FROM FARMERS, A PNRR OF WATER IS BEING ENCOURAGED

The plan of investments and incentives for water reuse is adopted by more than 90 percent of Puglian farmers. There was a change of hearts, and farmers are now looking forward to using water from water treatment plants in the Puglia region. More plants are already under construction to meet this huge demand. In 2021, only 5 plants were active in giving water for reuse. To date, in addition to the 18 projects already underway, all water treatment plants have been retrofitted. The impact is huge: from 2020 to now, water reuse has increased from 5% to 80%.

How was this possible?

Citizens first began to retrofit their homes for water reuse. Farmers, inspired by this exemplary behaviour, have aligned themselves in reusing water in their working environments as well.

Co-creation public engagement event report: Croatia

A live, online co-creation workshop was held on 19 October 2022 linked to the Galeb d.d. project demosite in Croatia. The same agenda structure was used: Starting with an overview of Project Ô, then a facilitated group discussion, a co-creation activity, and a concluding discussion about water sustainability in the local area.

Figure 10. Invitation and agenda screenshots for the co-creation workshop in Omiš, Croatia

Project Ô
Innovative circular water systems

You're invited to the online workshop

Introducing Project Ô

Developing practical tools for water sustainability

JOIN VIA ZOOM

DAY
19 October 2022

TIME
9:00 - 12:00 (CET)

ID Meeting: 874 5123 2425
Passcode: 680091
Link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/87451232425?pwd=a2dmakxGUTE3a2hkaVZmcFR0XhaZz09>

If you need more information, please send organiser Lall van zuydam (Institute for Methods Innovation) an email at lall@methodsinnovation.org

Workshop online
Introducing Project Ô: Developing practical tools for water sustainability

AGENDA:

- 09:00 Opening and introductions
- 09:15 Presentation of Project Ô
- 09:25 Discussion on water sustainability
- 10:00 Break
- 10:15 Co-creation activity: Create a news story
- 11:00 Break
- 11:15 Presentation of news stories
- 11:30 Final discussion and feedback
- 11:45 Closing

Project Ô
Innovative circular water systems

www.eu-project-o.eu

Image credit: Daniela Martin | Institute for Methods Innovation

Water Sustainability Context

In Croatia, the demosite focused on textile production. Every day, finite freshwater resources are used and discarded through unsustainable industrial production. It is especially important to reduce the impact of water-intensive industries, such as clothing. Galeb d.d., a clothing factory in Croatia, is working to increase the reuse of finite water resources by building its own water treatment plant. The technology module being deployed by Project Ô in this location is called PHOTO.CAT: This has been integrated into Galeb d.d.'s new water treatment plant. This photocatalytic unit is designed to remove harmful chemicals and organic pollutants and recover salts from the water.

The treatment process is designed to automatically mix different streams of treated water to ensure the right salt levels and temperatures for making clothing materials. These targeted treatments enable the factory's immediate reuse of the water, and also boost energy efficiency because the treated water is already optimised for clothing production.

The whole project is emphasising something that should be a focus for the textile industry in the upcoming years and decades.

Participant,
Croatia co-creation workshop

Water Sustainability Public Engagement Event

The live online co-creation workshop was designed, organised and conducted by the Institute for Methods Innovation. The workshop allowed Project Ô to identify attitudes and expectations, anxieties and pre-knowledge about sustainability aspects of water management among stakeholders from *Galeb d.d.* Twelve stakeholders participated in this event.

None of us is looking 50 or 100 years ahead [...] this is definitely something that needs to be talked about in the public [space] and people need to be aware that what they are doing today will impact future generations.

Participant,
Croatia co-creation workshop

Figure 11. Screenshot from the co-creation workshop in Omiš, Croatia

The screenshot displays a Zoom meeting interface. On the left, a blue and white slide titled "Welcome" features an agenda. The agenda items are:

- 09:00 Opening and introduction
- 09:15 Presentation of Project Ô and the need for water reuse
- 09:25 Discussion on water sustainability
- 10:00 Break
- 10:15 Co-creation activity: Create a news story
- 11:00 Presentation of news stories
- 11:30 Final discussion and feedback
- 11:45 Closing

At the bottom of the slide, logos for IMI (Institute for Methods Innovation), the website www.eu-project-o.eu, and Galeb d.d. are visible.

On the right side of the interface, a vertical list of participant names is shown, each with a small video thumbnail. The participants listed are:

- JELENAKOG
- JELENAKOG
- IMI (with a video thumbnail of a woman)
- Ivana Podrug (with a video thumbnail of a woman)
- Josip Aračić
- Josip Aračić
- ANTEMU
- ANTEMU
- Jelena Kristic

Co-Creation Group Discussion Findings

The group discussion portion of the workshop asked stakeholders to consider topics in-depth, including concerns over water scarcity and water quality, environmental concerns, and the need for public engagement.

Water Sustainability Concerns

Water scarcity and public awareness were the main concerns expressed by participants, as well as the **quality of the available water**. According to this participant, local citizens are not taking water scarcity seriously enough:

“There is not enough concern about water scarcity. This is because there are rivers and plenty of water sources in the area and people don’t realise how serious the situation really is.”

(Industry, Female)

“People do not have the mentality that water scarcity is possible because they have not experienced it.” (Industry, Female)

Furthermore, water quality and the protection of the environment is concerning, according to this participant:

“The quality of drinking water is the main concern. We must prioritise the protection of the environment around these water sources.” (Industry, Female)

In addition, the water reuse and circular water economy solutions should be promoted in Croatia, and the rest of the world:

“We need to promote a circular water economy and water reuse.”

(Industry, Female)

At this point, more of a concern is the quality of the water that we are drinking [...] at this time, that is the main concern.

Participant,
Croatia co-creation workshop

Water Sustainability Hopes and Expectations

One of the main hopes mentioned was to raise **public awareness** of the problem.

“Around the world, water scarcity should be talked about more so people know the potential threats.”
(Industry, Female)

I think the hope for everybody, not just in Croatia, but all around the world should be that we have to talk more about the potential problem of water scarcity.

Participant,
Croatia co-creation workshop

By working together and considering the needs of others, water conservation will be more achievable, according to this participant:

“People need to show more solidarity and think of others.”
(Industry, Female)

Furthermore, the textile industry in Croatia should invest in circular water economy solutions:

“More people should be aware of the importance of a circular water economy. This should also be the focus for the entire textile industry.” (Industry, Female)

Co-creation Activity Result

The final stage of the event was a co-creation activity in which participants were asked to create and share news stories about either the future of water sustainability in their local areas or Project Ô innovations at the demonstration site. The participants decided to write a press article on water treatment technologies used at *Galeb d.d.*. This particular story sheds light on their hopes to make a real impact on water sustainability and benefit their local communities by using, and possibly scaling up, water treatment technologies.

Figure 12. Fictional news created by participants in the co-creation workshop in Croatia

PROJECT Ô TECHNOLOGY IS GREAT FOR WATER PRESERVATION

Most production companies should be encouraged to implement technologies to ensure water sustainability and the protection of the environment. Technology is an effective way to preserve water. By implementing a circular water economy at Galeb, new input water isn't needed. Because production requires high volumes of water, this is a great start to saving water for the future. Furthermore, technology ensures that used water at Galeb is of better quality. There are also energy consumption savings and cost savings.

Co-creation public engagement event report: Israel

In Israel, the co-creation workshop was held on the 22 November 2022 with participants interested in the water sector in Israel (including Ardag Eilat, the Agriculture Ministry, the National Center for Mariculture, and NPO AquaculTech). The same structure was used for this event, including an informational overview of Project Ô, a facilitated group discussion, a co-creation activity, and a concluding discussion.

Figure 13. Invitation and agenda screenshots for the co-creation workshop in Eilat, Israel

You're invited to
the online workshop

Introducing Project Ô

Developing practical tools
for water sustainability

JOIN VIA ZOOM

DAY
22 November 2022

TIME
10:00 - 12:00 (Israel time)

ID Meeting: 864 6243 9565
Passcode: 248363
Link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/86462439565?pwd=TKwzak1seWJzeFhTR3dWL2tia2hZQT09>

If you need more information, please send organiser Lali van Zuydam (Institute for Methods Innovation) an email at lali@methodsinnovation.org

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www.eu-project-o.eu

Workshop online

Introducing Project Ô: Developing practical tools for water sustainability

AGENDA:

- 10:00 Opening and introductions
- 10:15 Presentation of Project Ô
- 10:25 Discussion on water sustainability
- 11:00 Break
- 11:15 Co-creation activity: Create a news story
- 11:00 Break
- 11:15 Presentation of news stories
- 11:30 Final discussion and feedback
- 11:45 Closing

Image credit: Daniela Martin | Institute for Methods Innovation

Local Water Sustainability Context

Fish farming systems are the fastest-growing food production sector in the world, providing 47% of global fish supplies. However, fish farms can produce the equivalent of 2.5 olympic swimming pools of wastewater daily, creating the conditions for significant negative environmental impacts. Traditionally, the water used in fish farming tanks is treated to convert harmful waste from fish into less toxic elements, called nitrates. Yet, these nitrates and other pollutants that remain in the water are typically released into lakes and oceans, where they can cause excessive algae and plant growth, overwhelming water-based ecosystems and harming wildlife. This is why new global environmental regulations require these nitrates to be removed from fish farming systems.

Project Ô's SALTECH technology module treats wastewater from land-based fish farms by removing nitrates, other pollutants, and excess salts from used water, which enables the water to be sustainably reused in fish tanks or to water plants. The technology also allows for valuable nutrients to be recovered from the wastewater, which can then be used as fish food or processed further to be used as biofuel or green fertilisers. Finally, the treatment process maintains a stable water temperature, which improves disease control management, resulting in bigger and healthier fish.

The SALTECH module is installed at the National Center for Mariculture in Israel. The technology can be used in any land-based mariculture location, even systems located away from coastal land. By using Project Ô water treatment technologies, water can be reused sustainably in fish farming systems, while using less water, making full use of available nutrients, and protecting the environment from the negative impacts of harmful wastewater, thereby reducing the demands on finite resources.

Water Sustainability Public Engagement Event

The group discussion portion of the workshop asked stakeholders to consider topics in-depth, including local water availability in the desert environment, reuse of water and other mariculture byproducts/nutrients, communication strategies to engage with the public and raise awareness, and benefits of engaging with circular water economy technologies, such as those used in Project Ô.

It's not only about recycling water, but nutrients as well.

Participant,
Israel co-creation
workshop

Water is something that has high value and we do appreciate each reuse for livelihood as well as various agricultural pathways.

Participant,
Israel co-creation workshop

Figure 14. Screenshot from the co-creation workshop in Eilat, Israel

Co-Creation Group Discussion Findings

Water Sustainability Concerns

According to participants, there are concerns over the **high cost of water resources**, water needed for **agricultural activities**, as well as the **deterioration of water quality** in the southern region of the country, where the city of Eilat is situated. This area is arid and freshwater sources are rare. Desalination and wastewater treatment in this area go back decades.

Freshwater is really rare [in the region], and over the past few decades, we desalinate water in order to make a living. And so from the very early stages, we had to put much emphasis on recirculating water.

Participant,
Israel co-creation workshop

We have a lack of enough water for the crops that we are growing.

Participant,
Israel co-creation workshop

This participant mentioned that water sustainability has been a concern for decades, because it is an arid area.

"It's a way of living in the Southern [region], it's a desert, freshwater is really rare, and over the past few decades, we desalinate water in order to make a living here in terms of human consumption and also for agriculture. And so from the very early stages, we had to put much emphasis on recirculating water." (Industry stakeholder, Israel)

Another industry stakeholder reinforced this notion, suggesting that there is a strong base of support for water reuse in southern Israel:

"Water is something that has high value and we do appreciate each reuse for livelihood as well as various agricultural pathways."

(Industry stakeholder, Israel)

A policy/government participant said that the longstanding agricultural use of water had caused concerns about the quality local water supplies:

"Another issue is the use of water here in the region, for agriculture, is causing slow but evident deterioration in the quality of the water because the water comes from local wells, local sources. Continuous use of this water is gradually increasing the salinity of the soil and the water and sustainability can only be achieved by using water treatment and other sources of water, national sources of water, which is already being done." (Policy/government stakeholder, Israel)

The use of water [in the region] for agriculture is causing slow but evident deterioration in the quality of the water because the water comes from local wells. Continuous use of this water is gradually increasing the salinity of the soil and the water, and sustainability can only be achieved by using water treatment and other sources of water.

Participant,
Israel co-creation workshop

Furthermore, this participant noted a need for water resources for agriculture in the Eilat region:

"We have a lack of enough water for the crops that we are growing." (Industry stakeholder, Israel)

Another concern, mentioned by this participant is the high cost of adopting circular water solutions:

"[...] technology must be cost-effective. Otherwise, it won't enable the users to carry on their activities. They need to be profitable [...]
So if costs [are] too high, it won't allow the implementation."
(Industry stakeholder, Israel)

This industry stakeholder said that the deployment of water management solutions that works for industry must account for issues of cost and logistics:

"[...] you might have your fish tanks in one place, but the water removal to another place, the freshwater needed in another area. And this adds to the complexity and to the cost because the water flows are not always synchronised [...]." (Industry stakeholder, Israel)

Water Sustainability Hopes and Expectations

Some of the hopes participants expressed include the possibility of **reusing water multiple times** and **creating alternative water loops**, such as those implemented as part of Project Ô.

This participant highlighted the value of engaging the local community about circular water economy solutions, as an important end-user:

"[Hope that] outreach and some educational programmes about water recycling projects and technologies to local schools and, of course, academia [will increase awareness about water-related issues]." (Industry stakeholder, Israel)

In the hopes section, maybe a little bit of outreach and some educational programmes about water recycling projects and technologies to local schools and of course academia.

Participant,
Israel co-creation workshop

Industry stakeholders consider water reuse technologies as crucial for water sustainability in mariculture:

"I would like to see recycling RAS [Recirculating Aquaculture System] happening in the area. The most sustainable systems are the ones that reuse [nearly] 100% of the water." (Industry stakeholder, Israel)

The project's circular water economy solution is designed to capitalise on the value of both recovering nutrients and water to maximise the benefits for industry users. Focus group participants highlighted the potential for multiple benefits to such water reuse solutions:

I would like to see recycling RAS [Recirculating Aquaculture System] happening in the area. The most sustainable systems are the ones that reuse [nearly] 100% of the water.

Participant,
Israel co-creation workshop

"It is about recycling water and nutrients as well." (Industry stakeholder, Israel)

Co-creation Activity Result

The final stage of the event was a co-creation activity in which participants were asked to create and share a news story about either the future of water sustainability in their local areas or Project Ô innovations at the demonstration site. The participants decided to write a press article about how Project Ô innovations create opportunities for improving sustainability and the environmental footprint at the demosite in Eilat. They also included ideas for potential future projects for the reuse of resources, such as sludge and seaweed. This particular story sheds light on their hopes to have a real impact on water sustainability in their region, benefiting all local communities.

Figure 15. News article created by participants in the co-creation workshop in Israel

PROJECT Ô TECHNOLOGIES TO REDUCE ENVIRONMENTAL FOOTPRINT

Project Ô technologies have created new opportunities at the National Center for Mariculture in Eilat, Israel.

By using Project Ô technologies, a variety of fish species can be cultivated. Currently carnivorous fish, such as seabream, are cultivated, but these have a higher environmental impact than herbivorous or omnivorous fish species. Because of the variety of technologies, new ways of treating water are possible, which can allow for the cultivation of multiple fish species, with different water salinity requirements.

Furthermore, because fish farming takes place on land, away from the ocean, there is a lower environmental impact because transport and shipping distances are reduced.

The National Center for Mariculture is satisfied with what has been achieved in terms of circular water economy solutions. According to site representatives, there is a 80% recovery rate of water and Project Ô

technologies are ready to be implemented in a scaled pilot system. The systems are also considered energy efficient because solar energy is being used.

Future opportunities for reuse include recovering materials from sludge, and using seaweed more widely, such as in the textile, cosmetics and bioplastics sectors.

Participant feedback survey

A feedback survey was designed and sent to all the public engagement event participants. The aim of this survey was to determine the effectiveness of the process and to improve the subsequent workshops. The most relevant results are summarised below.

Overall, most participants agreed that the events were important (90%), valuable (100%), useful (92%), relevant (100%) and fascinating (80%).

Figure 16. Participants' general feedback on the workshop (Likert scale)

In general, participants felt that they were able to actively participate (Figure 17) and that their contribution to the process was valued (Figure 18), which confirms that the expert event facilitators from IMI were critical to the success of the process.

Figure 17. 'I was able to actively participate' statement

Figure 18. 'My contribution to the process was valued' statement

When asked about factors that made it difficult for them to participate in the workshop, some participants mentioned lack of prior information as a major obstacle (Figure 19). These responses enabled the IMI team to provide more contextual information at the beginning of the events. This balanced the need to inform participants about relevant events in their community on the one hand, and the need to collect data on their own perspectives on the other.

Figure 19. 'I needed more information to fully participate' statement

International engagement events aimed at extended professional networks

As part of Project Ô's engagement and communication efforts in WP8, IMI organised two international events for extended professional networks with a focus on political communication and science advocacy relevant to water reuse. These events were foreseen in the project's Description of Action (DoA). They were public events focused on water sustainability-relevant themes such as public engagement and impact evaluation, and were enriched by the participation of internationally renowned academics and practitioners as speakers/facilitators.

Table 2. *International events overview*

International event theme	Date
Impact planning using logic models and theory of change	31 August 2022
How to make a difference in science policy with your research	21 November 2022

Participation

There was overwhelming demand to attend these international Project Ô events, greatly exceeding the attendance targets in the DoA. IMI invested considerable efforts in widely promoting the events, and had to add more spaces due to the resulting in very high demand.

Total attendance across the two international events was 536 participants, representing a wide range of professional backgrounds and organisations. Participants joined from all over the world, including the Americas (Canada, United States, Mexico, Venezuela, Brazil, Argentina, Chile, Colombia, Ecuador and Peru), Europe (Sweden, Finland, Poland, Germany, Belgium, France, Spain, Portugal, Switzerland, Italy, Ireland, Austria, Slovenia, Greece, Malta, Romania, Bulgaria and the UK), Africa (Nigeria, Zambia, Zimbabwe, South Africa, Ghana, Uganda and Kenya), Asia (Turkey, Israel, Saudi Arabia, India, Nepal, Indonesia, Philippines, South Korea and Japan) and Oceania (Australia and New Zealand).

Figure 20. Overview of countries of residence of webinar participants**Table 3.** Governmental institutions that participated in the webinar

Government	Country
European Food Safety Authority	Belgium
European Space Agency	Netherlands
District Institute of Science, Biotechnology and Health Innovation	Colombia
Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science	Ireland
Science Foundation Ireland	Ireland
Gencat - Information, procedures and services of the Government of Catalonia	Spain
Oceanic Platform of the Canary Islands	Spain
California Council on Science and Technology	United States
Health Security Agency	United Kingdom
Natural England	United Kingdom
Animal & Plant Health Agency	United Kingdom
Justice Department	United Kingdom
National Health Service	United Kingdom
Innovate UK	United Kingdom
UK Research and Innovation	United Kingdom
Environment Agency	United Kingdom
Department for International Trade	United Kingdom
Hackney Council	United Kingdom

Table 4. Universities that participated in the webinar

Universities	Country
Australian National University	Australia
Swinburne University of Technology	Australia
Monash University	Australia
Melbourne University	Australia
Griffith University	Australia
Ghent University	Belgium
EAFIT University	Colombia
Savonia University of Applied Sciences	Finland
Aalto University	Finland
Munster Technological University	Germany
Weihenstephan Triesdorf University of Applied Sciences	Germany
University College Dublin	Ireland
Trinity College Dublin	Ireland
Queen's University Belfast	Ireland
Maynooth University	Ireland
University College Cork	Ireland
Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland	Ireland
University of Galway	Ireland
University of Malta	Malta
National Autonomous University of Mexico (UNAM)	Mexico
Maastricht University	Netherlands
Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam	Netherlands
Technische Universiteit Delft	Netherlands
University of Otago	New Zealand
Otago Polytechnic	New Zealand
Wrocław University of Science and Technology	Poland
University of Aveiro	Portugal
University Institute of Lisbon	Portugal
University of Coimbra	Portugal
University of Bucharest	Romania
Nanyang Academy of Fine Arts	Singapore
National Institute of Education	Singapore
Stellenbosch University	South Africa
Lund University Centre for	Sweden

Sustainability Studies	
Bournemouth University	United Kingdom
University of Edinburgh	United Kingdom
The Open University	United Kingdom
Durham University	United Kingdom
University of Plymouth	United Kingdom
University of Derby	United Kingdom
University of Sussex	United Kingdom
Lancaster University	United Kingdom
University of Central Lancashire	United Kingdom
King's College London	United Kingdom
University College London	United Kingdom
University of Exeter	United Kingdom
University of Portsmouth	United Kingdom
University of Oxford	United Kingdom
Liverpool John Moores University	United Kingdom
University of Leeds	United Kingdom
Coventry University	United Kingdom
University of Bristol	United Kingdom
De Montfort University	United Kingdom
Swansea University	United Kingdom
University of the West of England	United Kingdom
University of Stirling	United Kingdom
Oxford Brookes University	United Kingdom
University of Liverpool	United Kingdom
London Metropolitan University	United Kingdom
University of South Wales	United Kingdom
Manchester Metropolitan University	United Kingdom
University of Bath	United Kingdom
University of Glasgow	United Kingdom
University of Cumbria	United Kingdom
University of Bradford	United Kingdom
University of Wolverhampton	United Kingdom
University of Suffolk	United Kingdom
University of Lincoln	United Kingdom
University of Warwick	United Kingdom
University of Sheffield	United Kingdom

University of St Andrews	United Kingdom
Heriot-Watt University	United Kingdom
British Columbia Institute of Technology	United Kingdom
University of Birmingham	United Kingdom
University of Hull	United Kingdom
Keele University	United Kingdom
Scotland's Rural College	United Kingdom
University of Gloucestershire	United Kingdom
St George's, University of London	United Kingdom
University of Nottingham	United Kingdom
Nottingham Trent University	United Kingdom
University of the West of Scotland	United Kingdom
Ulster University	United Kingdom
University of Kent	United Kingdom
University of Cambridge	United Kingdom
University of East Anglia	United Kingdom
University of York	United Kingdom
Cornell University	United States
Worcester Polytechnic Institute	United States
University of California, Berkeley	United States
West Virginia University	United States

Table 5. Research organisations that participated in the webinar

Research organisations	Country
Ludwig Boltzmann Gesellschaft (LBG)	Austria
European Lung Foundation	Belgium
European Southern Observatory	Germany
DBT/Wellcome Trust India Alliance	India
SFI Research Centre in Applied Geosciences	Ireland
ADAPT Research Centre	Ireland
National Children's Research Centre	Ireland
Engineers Ireland	Ireland
Early Childhood Ireland	Ireland
European Place Observing System	Italy
Mathematics Research Centre	Mexico
Wavec Offshore Renewables	Portugal
Calouste Gulbenkian Foundation	Portugal
Africa Health Research Institute	South Africa
Barcelona Supercomputing Centre	Spain
Schweizerische Akademie der Geistes- und Sozialwissenschaften	Sweden
Health Data Research UK	United Kingdom
Great Ormond Street Hospital Children's Charity	United Kingdom
The Francis Crick Institute	United Kingdom
The Alan Turing Institute	United Kingdom
National Institute for Health and Care Research	United Kingdom
The Bat Conservation Trust	United Kingdom
Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew	United Kingdom
South Downs National Park	United Kingdom
The Pirbright Institute	United Kingdom
The Zoological Society of London	United Kingdom
UK Energy Research Centre	United Kingdom
NFU Scotland	United Kingdom
The James Hutton Institute	United Kingdom
Wellcome Sanger Institute	United Kingdom
Sage Bionetworks	United States
Aspen Institute	United States

Table 6. Industry and services organisations that participated in the webinar

Industry and services	Country
Temaiken Bioparque	Argentina
Melbourne Water	Australia
Springer Nature	United Kingdom
Inscico	Germany
Analytic Translations	Germany
Zoho Corporation Pvt	India
Sector 3 Solutions Ltd	Ireland
Kinia Learning is Life	Ireland
Saint John of God Hospitaller Services Group	Ireland
Climate and Cities	United Kingdom
Marwell Wildlife	United Kingdom
Vertigo Ventures	United Kingdom
Mindfully Wired Communications	United Kingdom
Oxentia Limited	United Kingdom
Research Your Way	United Kingdom
Covalent Creative Partnerships Ltd	United Kingdom
Brooke Hospital for Animals	United Kingdom
Gweld Communications Ltd	United Kingdom
Just Economics LLC	United States
Virgin Media	United States
STEAM Workgroup	United States
Connecticut Academy of Science and Engineering	United States

International event details: Impact planning using logic models and theory of change

On Wednesday 31 August 2022, a Project Ô-organised webinar was offered on the topic of impact planning using logic models and theory of change. It was organised primarily by the Institute for Methods Innovation on behalf of the project, working in collaboration with a company focused on research impact (Fast Track Impact) and its highly-cited CEO Professor Mark Reed.

Using water sustainability examples from Project Ô and other projects, the workshop introduced participants to powerful tools that will enable them to think systematically about their pathway to impact, including risks and assumptions they might need to take into account and indicators to help them track their progress.

Figure 21. “Impact planning using logic models and theory of change” webinar header

Image credit: Daniela Martin | Institute for Methods Innovation

Professor Mark Reed (Scotland's Rural College and Fast Track Impact) introduced participants to logic models based on his widely used impact planning template and his approach to stakeholder analysis. Dr Eric Jensen (Institute for Methods Innovation and Project Ô) introduced the theory of change approach that IMI uses to deliver evidence-based research impact activities. Prof. Reed explained how participants could co-produce a more detailed theory of change with stakeholders, and Dr. Jensen showed how theory of change can be used to evaluate impact, using a water research case study. Participants had the

opportunity to see examples of logic models and theory of change developed with researchers by Sarah Bowman (Trinity College Dublin)³.

Figure 22. “Impact planning using logic models and theory of change” webinar screenshots

³ Recording of the workshop is available on YouTube: https://youtu.be/m_jsRdQ1_xs

International event details: How to make a difference in science policy with your research

A second Project Ô-organised international event was organised for 21 November 2022 on the topic, How to make a difference in science policy with research⁴. It was organised by the Institute for Methods Innovation on behalf of the project, with the invited speaker, renowned science policy strategist and organiser of the Science Policy Bootcamp in the United States, Dr Andrew George (Sigma Xi scientific honours society). This live event was aimed at water sustainability researchers, professionals and others interested in the links between research, innovation and public policy.

Figure 23. “How to make a difference in science policy with your research” event header

Image credit: Daniela Martin | Institute for Methods Innovation

The event addressed how researchers can make an effective plan for creating policy impact. It introduced the differences in culture between research and policy and provided tools to chart pathways to public policy impact. Dr Andrew George (Sigma Xi, a scientific society in the United States) introduced the cultural differences between research and innovation, and policy, based on his time establishing the North Carolina STEM Policy Fellowship and as a strategy consultant for the U.S. government's National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration. Dr Eric A. Jensen (IMI/Project Ô) introduced concepts such as policy impact objectives, impact logic models and theories of change, showing

⁴ Recording of the workshop is available on YouTube: <https://youtu.be/iuX68afwtmc>

how to use these concepts to develop policy impacts from research and innovation actions. Dr Jensen and Dr George provided concrete examples, drawing on their research and policy work, with Dr Jensen highlighting examples from Project Ô.

Figure 24. Screenshots from the “How to make a difference in science policy with your research” webinar

IMI Institute for Methods Innovation

Co-producing a Theory of Change

Bottom-up:

- Stakeholder and partner identification
- Complete impact planning templates with partners
- Thematically group impact goals
- Arrange impact goals in causal chains
- Look back to activities in templates to further trace back to research

Participants in the Zoom meeting: Daniela Martin, Dr Eric A. Jensen, Joan Centrella, Andrew George, ANA CLAUDIA..., Christian Todota.

This live online workshop had the number of ‘seats’ restricted to ensure Dr Jensen and Dr George could offer sufficient support to participants to start developing their policy impact theory of change.